

CHET TILLARINI O'QITISH TEXNIKASI MASALASI

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Xorijiy til mugaxassisi xorijiy tillarni o'qitish uslubiyoti fani yutuqlarini o'zlashtirgan va to'plagan tajribasi orqali o'quvchining tilga munosabati me'yorinianiqlash qilish, uni yanada takomillashtirish kabi psixik va metodik jarayonlarini umumlashtiradi. Kasb hunar maktabni bitirupchilarni chet tilini nechog'lik bilishi ma'lum darajada bo'lgusi mutahassislarning intellektual, hamda professional, saviyasining o'sishiga, O'zbekistonni xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan madaniy, iqtisodiy va siyosiy aloqalarini rivojlanishiga bog'liq.

Shu sababli keyingi paytlarda Respublikamiz diqqati chet tillarni o'qitish usullarini takomillashtirishga, sifatini oshirishga alohida e'tibor bermoqda. Chet tili o'qitishni takomillashtirishda zamonaviy texnik vositalardan, shu jumledan, kompyuter va internet tarmoqlaridan foydalanish zarurati tug' ilmoqda.

Chet tili darslarida kompyuterni o'qitish dasturlari bilan ishlash shakllariga quyidagilar kiradi: so'z boyligini o'rganish; talaffuz qilishni mashq qilish; dialogik va monologik nutqni o'rgatish; yozishni o'rgatish; grammatik hodisalarni ishlab chiqish. Internet-resurslardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari juda katta. Global Internet dunyoning istalgan nuqtasida joylashgan talabalar va o'qituvchilar uchun zarur bo'lgan har qanday ma'lumotni olish uchun sharoit yaratadi:

Mintaqaviy geografik materiallar, yoshlar hayotidagi yangiliklar, gazeta va jurnallardan maqolalar va boshqalar. Darslarda ingliz tilida Internet yordamida bir qator didaktik muammolarni hal qilish mumkin: global tarmoq materiallaridan foydalanib o'qish ko'nikma va malakalarini shakllantirish; maktab o'quvchilarining yozish qobiliyatini oshirish; talabalarning so'z boyligini to'ldirish; talabalarning ingliz tilini o'rganish motivasiyasini shakllantirish. Bundan tashqari, bu ish maktab o'quvchilarining ufqini kengaytirish, ingliz tilida so'zlashadigan mamlakatlarda

tengdoshlari bilan ishbilarmonlik munosabatlari va aloqalarini o'rnatish va qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun Internet-texnologiyalar imkoniyatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Talabalar Internetda o'tkaziladigan testlar, viktorinalar, tanlovlar, olimpiadalarda ishtirok etishlari, boshqa mamlakatlardagi tengdoshlari bilan yozishmalar, suhbatlar, videokonferensiyalar va h.k.larda qatnashishlari mumkin. Talabalar hozirda loyihada ishlayotgan muammo haqida ma'lumot olishlari mumkin. Ommaviy kompyuterlashtirishning mazmunli asoslari zamonaviy kompyuter aqliy mehnat sharoitlarini, umuman, uning har qanday ko'rinishini optimallashtirishning samarali vositasi ekanligi bilan bog'liq. Kompyuterning bir o'ziga xos xususiyati bor, uni boshqalarga o'rgatish uchun vosita sifatida va bilimlarni egallashda yordamchi sifatida ishlatishda aniqlanadi, bu uning jonsizligi. Mashina foydalanuvchi bilan "do'stona" aloqada bo'lishi mumkin va ba'zi paytlarda uni "qo'llab-quvvatlaydi", ammo u hech qachon g'azablanish alomatlarini ko'rsatmaydi va sizni zerikkan deb his qilishingizga imkon bermaydi. SHu ma'noda, kompyuterlardan foydalanish, ehtimol o'qitishning ayrim jihatlarini individualizatsiya qilishda eng foydalidir. Kasb hunar maktablarida chet tilini o'rganishning asosiy maqsadi kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishdir, boshqa barcha maqsadlar (tarbiyalash, o'qitish, rivojlantirish) ushbu asosiy maqsadni amalga oshirish jarayonida amalga oshiriladi. Kommunikativ yondashuv muloqotni o'rgatish va Internet faoliyatining asosi bo'lgan madaniyatlararo ta'sir o'tkazish qobiliyatini shakllantirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Aloqa tashqarisida Internetning ma'nosi yo'q - bu xalqaro ko'p millatli, madaniyatlararo jamiyatdir, uning hayoti dunyodagi millionlab odamlarning elektron aloqasiga asoslangan bo'lib, bir vaqtning o'zida gaplashmoqda - bu sodir bo'lgan ishtirokchilar soni va hajmi bo'yicha eng katta suhbat. Unga darsda qatnashish xorijiy til, biz haqiqiy aloqa modelini yaratamiz.

Hozirgi vaqtda aloqa, interaktivlik, muloqotning haqiqiyliги, madaniy sharoitda tilni o'rganish, ta'limning avtonomligi va insonparvarligi masalalariga ustuvor ahamiyat berilmoqda. Ushbu tamoyillar madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani

kommunikativ qobiliyatning tarkibiy qismi sifatida rivojlantirishga imkon beradi. Chet tillarni o'qitishning yakuniy maqsadi chet tilidagi muhitda erkin yo'nalishni va turli vaziyatlarda etarli darajada javob berish qobiliyatini o'rgatishdir, ya'ni. aloqa. Bugungi kunda Internet resurslaridan foydalangan holda yangi usullar an'anaviy chet tillarini o'qitishga qarshi. Chet tilida muloqotni o'rgatish uchun siz materialni o'rganishni rag'batlantiradigan va etarli xulq-atvorni rivojlantiradigan haqiqiy, haqiqiy hayotiy vaziyatlarni yaratishingiz kerak (ya'ni aloqa haqiqiyliги prinsipi deb ataladi). Yangi texnologiyalar, xususan Internet ushbu xatoni tuzatishga harakat qilmoqda. Kommunikativ yondashuv - bu materialni ongli ravishda anglashga va u bilan ishlash usullariga, muloqotga psixologik va lingvistik tayyorgarlikni yaratishga qaratilgan muloqotni simulyasiya qiluvchi strategiya.

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